

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS AND PARENTS IN INCULCATING VALUE EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Value education means inculcating in the students, a sense of humanism, a deep concern for the well being of others and the nation. Value education teaches us to preserve whatever is good and worthwhile in what we have inherited from our culture. In ancient India, the Vedas, the Upanishads, the Epics manifested and upheld the values of Indian society. There the meaning of value is widely accepted as *Satyam*, *Shivam* and *Sundaram*. More importance was given to morality, honesty, duty, truth, friendship, brotherhood, etc. They were the themes of Indian culture and society. Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, our honorable president in his book "India 2020: A Vision of the New Millennium" has rightly remarked that "If you are a teacher in whatever capacity, you have a very special role to play because more than anybody else it is you who are shaping the future generation. A teacher has a higher responsibility as compared to other professionals as students look upon the teacher as an embodiment of perfection. Gautama Buddha has rightly preached "Desire is the root cause of Evil". Students are told not to fulfill their desires by improper ways, by adhering to immoral activities. The present paper is an attempt to state the importance of value education so that the future generations will nourish high ideals and values to contribute in the development of the society and the role of teachers and parents in imparting values.

Key Words: Character - Building, Ethics, Gurukul System, Torch-Bearers & Virtues and Vices

Introduction:

Education without vision is waste, education without value is crime, and education without mission is life burden:

Values are the guiding principles of life that contribute to the all round development of an individual. It is the part and parcel of the philosophy of nation and that of education system. They give a direction to life and thus bring joy, satisfaction and peace. Values add quality to life. Thus, we can say that any human activity, thought or idea, feeling, sentiment or emotion, which promotes self development of an individual, constitutes a value. The other corresponding function of a value is that it should also contribute to the welfare of the family, the community and the nation. Value system is the backbone of the society. Values may vary from one society to another and from time to time. But, every society abides by certain moral values, and these values are accepted by all the societies as Global values. "Parents are a child's first teachers and role models." They are responsible for shaping up the child's behavior and implementing positive values in them. Children listen, observe and imitate their parents. So it is important that they should be good role models the kids would want to follow. As a Mother or Father, a Parent has to practice what she/he preaches to expect the child to follow it.

Education has become a business today. This has changed the outlook of the students as well as the parents and it has further resulted in deterioration of respect for teachers and all those who are a part and parcel of education system. Imparting value education and reforming the society were the only aims and objectives of the teachers of ancient age. But in the present scenario, due to manifold changes in various aspects of our civilization such as population explosion, advancement in science and technology, knowledge expansion, rapid industrialization, urbanization, mobilization, IT revolution, liberalization, privatization & globalization as well as the influence of western culture, present society has become highly dynamic. Growing global poverty, pollution, hunger, disease, unemployment, unsociability, caste system, child labour, gender inequality, ill-treatment of women, violence, disability, exploitation of natural resources and many such evils have caused value- crisis on the globe, adversely affecting the core human values such as honesty, sincerity, morality and humanity. To overcome the problems of the present era, inculcation of values among individuals and promotion of values in educational system, as well as society, is highly essential.

Good manners are not taught through formal teaching. They are acquired more by observation:

It is therefore imperative that parents are very cautious. Children are very smart and observant. Whatever the parents do or talk, they mimic their parents. You must have noticed that children generally speak in the same tone and manner in which their parents speak. Good manners are not taught through formal teaching. They are acquired more by observation. The parent should not give too many instructions to the children. Allow the child to learn from your manners rather than lecture.

Importance of Value Education: In the context of social changes education is not only to impart information and to teach skills to the students but also to inculcate the values of humanism, democracy, socialism,

secularism and national integration. This is necessary for the realization of our national objectives of building a democratic and just social order based on equality, social justice, fraternity and freedom. We know that India was a very rich country in cultural heritage and spiritual aspects. But now it has become a nation of violence, terrorism, extremism, corruption etc. As a student of Philosophy, I can say that to remove all these from our society value oriented education is highly needed. In the current times, Teachers concentrate on imparting technical education to their students so that the increasing needs of the information technology (IT) industry are met with the students. Success is perceived in terms of equipping students with scientific and technical knowledge rather than in developing human beings who possess a sound understanding of good human values. Education is not just about learning skills (how to) but also about the ability to decide on what (what to do?) and why (why to do?). It should lead to the development of critical ability in students towards distinguishing between essence and form, or between what is of value and what is superficial in life. It should develop their understanding which is a pre-requisite for a movement from a rule based society to a relationship based society. Developing the right understanding about oneself and the rest of reality through self exploration and realization of the inherent co- existence, harmony and self-regulation at various levels of existence is seen to be the real basis of imbibing universal human values and ethical human conduct. This is what will affect transformation towards a holistic worldview (human consciousness) which happens to be the prime purpose of value education. Values are a set of desirable behaviour which is good for the individual and also the society. In this respect we find the relevance of the saying- Values are not taught, lectured about or professed, they are only demonstrated. The parents and teachers make maximum impact on the personality of an individual in the formative years of life which remains all through the life. In order to train students on importance of good human values, educational institutions such as school, colleges and universities need good teachers and mentors who can serve as role models. Training of teachers is an extremely important pre-requisite for implementation of any value education program in any institution. Just as for a course on engineering design, it is important that the teacher himself should be a good designer, it is even more important that a teacher involved in value education is himself a value driven person. Teachers of value education have necessarily to be role models for their students.

After attaining independence, no doubt, the nation made rapid development in all fields, but we lost our character and pride in our values. It is rightly said- if wealth is lost, nothing is lost.; if health is lost, something is lost; but, if character is lost, everything is lost. This holds true not only for individuals, but also for the society. We can express the need of values as follows-

- ✓ To guide the human beings in the right path, to inculcate the concept of Universal Brotherhood and to achieve the absolute values of Truth, Goodness and Beauty;
- ✓ To give direction and firmness to life and bring joy, satisfaction and peace of life to preserve our culture and heritage and to develop morality and character;
- ✓ To bring the behavioural changes towards positivism;
- ✓ To promote the peace and harmony in the individuals and society;
- ✓ To bring the quality of life and sustainable development in the society.

Above all, the most important need is to inculcate the core values such as truth, righteousness, peace, love and non-violence among the people to make them good human beings in true sense.

Education should foster universal and eternal values, and be oriented towards the unity and integration of our people. It is therefore, essential to explore and identify the concrete devices for the incorporation of values in education. Educational institutions can inculcate value education through the following ways and means-

- ✓ Cleanliness programme in the institution;
- ✓ Community service programmes;
- ✓ Social service programmes;
- ✓ First-aid programmes;
- ✓ Celebration of national days and festivals, dramas depicting values;
- ✓ Student participation or self-government in institutions;
- ✓ Silent meditation;
- ✓ Observation of punctuality by all;
- ✓ Equal treatment to all in the institutions;
- ✓ Lecture or talks emphasizing on the unity of all religions, harmony and national integration;

Setting good examples of conduct and behaviour by the teachers which may be imbibed by the students in themselves.

Gurukul System:

The traditional Gurukul system of imparting education transformed the personality of the pupils. Spiritual wisdom was imparted to them through spiritual gurus. Thus a strong foundation of ethical values was laid down. Guru's prepared students to become responsible citizens and contribute in social welfare. They could channelize their energy for the betterment of the society. Positive vibes coming from the inner spirit infused in them high regard for spiritual aspects. Gurus imparted knowledge of past, present and future. They were known

as Trikalajananis. Education stood for emancipation, ennoblement and evolution of human beings. Lord Krishna also studied in the Gurukul system. Sandipani Rishi imparted knowledge to him and other students. We have examples of Buttoo, Arjun, who studied in Gurukul system.

Present Education System: Dearth of Value Education:

Present education system deals with imparting knowledge of “Apara Vidya” i.e. study of Physics, Chemistry, history, biology etc; as well knowledge of scriptures and Vedas. The knowledge which we possess through the present education system is Apara Vidya which means that although we have knowledge of the world we do not have knowledge of our own self, of the supreme reality which is beyond time and space. We get knowledge of the external world. Today’s education system is designed in such a way that a human being will achieve materialistic success and superficial achievements but he will lack virtues like kindness, honesty, compassion, righteousness, peace, love, non-violence etc. Human beings have become individualistic and self-centered. This infuses in them jealousy, Hatred and rivalry. Stability of society is threatened by the breakdown of ethics. The basic aim of education should be to produce men of knowledge and culture. Values such as Patriotism, anti-untouchability, dignity of individuals, endurance, social service, justice, national integration find no place in today’s world of corruption, violence, intolerance and money-making.

Value Education: Need of the Hour:

Values are standards or principles considered important in life. They come from within and also by practicing. They are the foundation of human existence. Without the knowledge of values society cannot sustain. Values tell a man to differentiate between good and bad, what one should do and what one should abstain from. They make our life meaningful. Due to dearth of values in the present generation the curriculum must give prominence to value education. Value education has never been out of style. It is very relevant in almost all the fields concerning human activity. Dr. Gururaj Karajagi, Academic Director of Jain International Residential School, Bangalore states the dichotomy staring at us in life. He says we have outstanding doctors who are in to organ robbery, brilliant engineers whose bridges collapses soon after their bills are passed, accountants who rob government treasury by manipulation, civil servants who rule as emperors, politicians with fake promises. All of them are best educated and trained but their intellectual dishonesty is horrifying.

Role of Teachers and Parents:

Teachers’ role is very vital in moulding the future of a country and, as such, it is considered the noblest profession. Teachers are the ideals to their pupils. An educational institute should not be just confined to teaching and learning but it should be considered as a place where consciousness is aroused and illumined; soul is purified and strengthened. It is the place where the seeds of discipline, devotion and commitment are planted and fostered with deliberate efforts. A constructive companionship between teachers and students has to be developed. In a nutshell, a teacher in real sense is one who himself practices the human values. He should walk his talk to leave an ever lasting impression in the minds of students. Teaching is not a job; it is an attitude. Teacher is a source of information, a guide, a mentor, a surrogate parent, a motivator, all at the same time. Teaching is the only profession which always deals with the future. To be an ideal teacher, who can be a role model, one should ask himself three questions before taking up this noble profession.

- ✓ *Do you love your subject?* Anyone who does not love his subject can never be a good teacher and cannot inspire his students.
- ✓ *Do you love your profession?* If one does not have the respect for his vocation, he can never have self-esteem of himself. Such teachers do not discharge confidence and assurance.
- ✓ *Can you love your students as intensely as your own children?* Anyone who cannot love his students as his own cannot become a great teacher. All the greatest Masters in the world have demonstrated this remarkable quality of loving their disciples unconditionally.

Confucius has outlined the ethics of teaching in three beautiful words.

Ren - which means an act of utmost love.

Yi - refers to moral uprightness.

Li - indicates etiquettes in personal and institutional life.

According to Confucian theory, only a person who is always a source of love, morally upright and whose behaviour not only in personal but also in the institutional life is perfect, is worthy of being a teacher.

House is the first learning environment for the child and parents are the first teachers. They not only guide the child in its progressive path but also demonstrate the appropriate behaviour by their actions. Normally we come across three categories of parents.

(a) Over Possessive: This situation normally prevails in unitary families. In these days of small families, the parents would have one or at best two children. They become highly concerned about these children, who is natural but they become over possessive, which is detrimental to the growth of the child. They would try to do everything for the child without allowing him to do or experiment something on his own. In this overflowing flood of concern, they pamper the child, overlook his omissions and start supporting him even when he needs correction.

b) Indifferent: This second type of parents is not much concerned about the child. It does not mean that they do not love the child. Either, they are illiterates or too busy persons. Some of them do not have the methods and tools to handle their children and some do not have the time to guide and manage the children.

c) Overpowering: These parents desire to bring up their children under 'total discipline'. They expect the child to be always immaculate and faultless in every action and situation. They cannot tolerate anything otherwise. They are very critical and keep on pointing the finger of accusation at the child. They take all decisions about the child and truly believe that the child cannot and should not take decisions.

The classification mentioned above is not necessarily a watertight compartment. These are the general types. The idea is to have a good blend of all the above types. We believe that handling of a child by the parent should be with an iron hand in a velvet gloves. Iron hand is too hard and harsh. It hurts. Velvet glove is too soft and is incapable of holding anything firmly and guide. Only an iron hand in a velvet glove can provide the necessary firm guidance without being unduly harsh. We have seen many children who defy all systems and become too selfish. They normally come out from the family of over possessive parents. They are used to the pampering of the parents so much so that they expect the same thing from the world at large. They get hurt very quickly. Children coming out of the houses managed by the overpowering parents would become either oversensitive and introverts or totally immune to criticism. Those children who are not guided properly are left to fend themselves. What a person becomes when he grows up is very largely determined by the upbringing. What the parents did is more important than what they said, because, the child learns by observing and not just by listening. An alcoholic or a smoker cannot advise his child not to drink or smoke etc. Parents have no options but to become role models.

Conclusion:

When a problem arises, it needs to be recognized, addressed and resolved. Instead of blaming people or institutions for the results of a lack of morality in schools, we should focus our efforts on finding ways of successfully implementing character education into schools. Changes have to occur in parents, legislators, communities, and the media and educational system so that children are taught how to behave. We, the parents should remember that our kid's good habits always begin at home. Because, a good habit for children helps our child grow up soon and be a wonderful and successful human being. Make sure you are there throughout to guide and support him or her. Actualizing character education programs into schools is necessary in order to overcome this nation's crisis of character. Thus Teachers and parents both play an important role in the nation building by character building of the students and the children. The best and the greatest profession in the world is that of a teacher, because the future of a nation depends upon the type of teachers who shape the future generations. Every teacher plays the most important role in shaping the students as enlightened citizen. Swami Vivekananda's words should not be forgotten by the teachers- "Arise, Awake and Stop not till the goal are achieved".

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